

STUDY OF THE EFFECT OF THE SUBSTANCE "ALFAMANKOR" ON HEPG2 CELLS

Khayrullaev D.K.

Gulyamov Sh.Sh.

Zakirova R.Yu.

Jumaboev F.R.

Sharipov A.T.

Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute, Tashkent city, Republic of Uzbekistan

e-mail: ruxsonaz@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17342878>

Relevance: Liver cancer, particularly hepatocellular carcinoma (HepG2), is one of the most common cancers worldwide, with a high mortality rate. Current chemotherapeutic agents often have significant side effects, and their effectiveness is limited. Therefore, the search for new, effective, and less toxic compounds is considered a key area of research in oncology.

Main compounds, particularly biologically active substances containing metal ions, can disrupt cellular redox homeostasis and activate apoptosis. The Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute has developed a complex compound based on alpha-lipoic acid, known as "Alfamankor" which has specific antiproliferative and cytotoxic properties. Studying its effect on HepG2 cells may open up new therapeutic options for the treatment of liver cancer.

Purpose of the study: To evaluate the cytotoxic and antiproliferative effect of the complex compound "Alfamankor" against human hepatocellular carcinoma cells (HepG2) in vitro, and to determine its potential therapeutic value.

Materials and methods: *Cell culture:* The human hepatocellular carcinoma cell line HepG2 was maintained in Dulbecco's modified medium (DMEM) supplemented with 10% FBS and 1% penicillin-streptomycin at 37°C in a humidified incubator with 5% CO₂.

Cell viability analysis: HepG2 cells were seeded at a density of 15,000 cells/well in 96-well plates and incubated for 24 hours. The cells were then treated with Alfamankor at various concentrations (50, 75, 100, 125, and 150 µM) for 24 hours. After incubation, cell viability was assessed using the Cell Counting Kit-8 (CCK-8, Dojindo, Japan). Ten microliters of CCK-8 solution were added to each well and incubated for another 3 hours at 37°C. Absorbance was measured at 450 nm using an ELMR-112 microplate reader (Scitek Global Co., Ltd.). Experiments were performed in triplicate, and viability was calculated as a percentage relative to untreated control cells.

Results: Effect of Alfamankor on HepG2 Cell Viability: The cytotoxicity of Alfamankor against HepG2 cells was assessed after 24-hour exposure using the CCK-8 assay. Treatment with Alfamankor resulted in a clear, dose-dependent reduction in cell viability, with an IC₅₀ value calculated at approximately 36.8 µM. Significant cytotoxicity was observed at concentrations starting at 50 µM, with cell viability consistently below 50%, indicating high anticancer efficacy in this hepatocellular carcinoma cell line. This study evaluated the anticancer activity of Alfamankor against the human hepatocellular carcinoma cell line HepG2, which demonstrated significant cytotoxic potential, reflected by an IC₅₀ value of approximately 36.8 µM.

Conclusions: The obtained results indicate that Alfamankor has potential therapeutic efficacy in the treatment of liver cancer, especially considering its pronounced efficacy at lower micromolar concentrations.